

URBCON

By-products for sustainable concrete in the urban environment

WP LT - Deliverable LT.4.1

POLICY REVIEW

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Executive Summary

Based on an extensive literature review, the aim of this report has been to understand the policy context in which the URBCON project eventually will be operating in. Which policies at EU, national and local level are in favour of the URBCON concept and can support and drive the further uptake of the URBCON concept, and which potential barriers the project will face in terms of legislation, economic, institutional, environmental and social.

The report concludes that the main drivers identified of direct importance for the URBCON concept originates from Climate Policies and the obligations to the Paris agreement of reducing GHG emissions by 40% in 2030 and to become climate neutral by 2050. Operationalisation of the Paris Agreement has for the EU resulted in a number of Policies, Roadmaps and initiatives such as the Green Deal, the Circular Economic Action Plan, etc. all with the overall aim to reduce CO₂ emissions, and decouple economic activity from depletion of natural capital.

Climate related policies has been assessed from EU-, national- and local level.

The assessment of literature concerning barriers and enablers provides a solid overview of potential pitfalls and challenges of both technical, legislative, economic and social nature. An internal URBCON study related to Social Acceptance of Eco-concrete likewise revealed a number of recommendations for how to overcome different type of barriers.

This combination allowed us to identify a number of Policy gaps, which we are putting forward as Policy Recommendations. Policies of both soft and hard nature that will be necessary in order to get the circular economy agenda rolling including concepts such as URBCON.

The main policy recommendations include:

- Encourage use of secondary raw materials, either through taxes on virgin materials, or by making LCA, carbon footprint compulsory for all building products
- Promote use of Material Passport
- Initiate measures, e.g. demonstrations to convince key stakeholders that low-carbon cement types can replace many traditional OPC applications, e.g. tiles, flooring, façade panels
- Allow new types of low carbon cements to be tested and assessed on same terms as current OPC by shifting towards Performance-based building standards
- To encourage stakeholders: architects, civil engineering, construction companies, certification schemes, etc to consider low carbon cements through more demonstrations/reference projects, training and communication and Green Public Procurement

Table of Contents

1	<u>INTRODUCTION</u>	5
1.1	AIM OF THE DELIVERABLE	5
1.2	OUTLINE OF THE DOCUMENT	5
1.3	METHODOLOGY.....	5
2	<u>DRIVERS SUPPORTING TRANSITION TO CIRCULAR ECONOMY</u>	6
2.1	BARRIERS AND ENABLERS.....	7
2.2	SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE OF ECO-CONCRETE	9
3	<u>OVERVIEW OF RELEVANT EU POLICIES</u>	13
3.1	CLIMATE.....	13
3.2	CIRCULAR ECONOMY	15
4	<u>POLICIES IMPLEMENTED AT NATIONAL AND REGIONAL LEVEL.....</u>	17
4.1	THE NETHERLANDS.....	18
4.1.1	CLIMATE.....	18
4.1.2	CIRCULAR ECONOMY	20
4.2	BELGIUM.....	22
4.2.1	CLIMATE	22
4.2.2	CIRCULAR ECONOMY	23
4.3	FLANDERS.....	23
4.3.1	CLIMATE	23
4.3.2	CIRCULAR ECONOMY	24
4.4	GERMANY	24
4.4.1	CLIMATE.....	24
4.4.2	CIRCULAR ECONOMY	28
4.5	UNITED KINGDOM.....	29
4.5.1	CLIMATE.....	29
4.5.2	CIRCULAR ECONOMY.....	31
5	<u>POLICIES IMPLEMENTED AT CITY LEVEL.....</u>	33
5.1	ROTTERDAM	33
5.1.1	CLIMATE.....	33
5.1.2	CIRCULAR ECONOMY.....	33
5.2	CITY OF GHENT	35

5.2.1	CLIMATE	35
5.2.2	CIRCULAR ECONOMY	36
5.3	PRIVATE INITIATIVES.....	37
6	<u>STANDARDISATION, PRIVATE INITIATIVES AND STATUS ON CIRCULARITY</u>	<u>39</u>
6.1	STANDARDISATION AND REGULATIONS.....	39
6.2	STATUS OF CIRCULAR ECONOMY - HOW FAR ARE WE AND HOW DO WE MEASURE PROGRESS	40
6.2.1	CIRCULARITY INDICATORS	40
7	<u>POLICY GAPS AND RECOMMENDATIONS.....</u>	<u>44</u>
7.1	POLICY GAPS	44
7.1.1	CIRCULAR ECONOMY INDICATORS & MONITORING.....	44
7.1.2	ECONOMIC INCENTIVES FOR INNOVATION.....	44
7.1.3	TAXES	44
7.1.4	PUBLIC PROCUREMENT	45
7.1.5	INFORMATION & DATA	46
7.1.6	SOCIAL/CULTURAL/ BEHAVIORIAL.....	47
7.2	URBCON POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS.....	48
8	<u>CONCLUSIONS</u>	<u>52</u>
9	<u>REFERENCES.....</u>	<u>53</u>

1 Introduction

1.1 Aim of the Deliverable

The aim of this deliverable is to make a review of the main policies at EU, National and City level influencing and driving the transition to a circular economy, and hence having an influence of the uptake of the URBCON concept and technologies in both a positive and negative direction.

The outcome of the assessment is to identify the main policy gaps currently existing that might prevent the potential uptake of the URBCON concepts and on this background to propose a number of Policy recommendations.

1.2 Outline of the document

Chapter 2 outlines and discusses some of the main drivers for the transition to a circular economy as well as both enablers and barriers.

Chapter 3 provides a review of relevant EU policies, notably the Green Deal.

Chapter 4 looks specifically at national policies related to the Green Transition.

Chapter 5 focuses on 4 different city strategies or roadmaps related to circular Economic Action Plans.

Chapter 6 includes a brief status related to regulation, private initiatives and circularity of relevance for determining the main Policy Gaps

Chapter 6 identifies and discusses main Policy Gaps leading to a number of Policy recommendations of direct importance for the URBCON case.

Chapter 7 concludes the report.

1.3 Methodology

The methodology applied throughout this report is based on an extensive literature review combined with internal project partners discussion and expertise.

The reviewed policies are divided in two topics: Climate and Circular Economy. Both are relevant and applicable for the URBCON project since the project targets both the use of secondary raw materials and reduction in CO2 emissions. Since the URBCON project is operative on multiple layers of governmental bodies, the review follows a top-down approach: Global > EU > National > Local.

The Green Transition is used as a broader concept embracing also Circular Economy.

2 Drivers supporting transition to Circular Economy

There are two overall prevailing circumstances driving our societies transition from linear to a circular economy. These are first and foremost the overarching goal to cut CO₂ to at least 55% compared to 1990 by 2030 and to reach climate neutrality by 2050 in order to meet the target of the Paris agreement. The other main pressure for change is driven by the need to reduce the consumption of the Earth’s natural resources.

From these overarching goals and ambitions, drivers for change can be grouped into different headings. Policies has been formulated at global, EU, national and regional level for how to reach the climate goals for where the transition to Circular Economy has been identified as a critical systemic change.

The market is made up by all the consumers and constitutes another important driver for the transition, e.g., consumers are increasingly demanding low carbon products, and are increasingly demanding climate action now. The corporate world is also responding to the climate goals and corporate strategies are being reformulated to incorporate climate neutrality. Reducing CO₂ footprint is driving the agenda and in many cases circular economic thinking has even proved to be good for the bottom line and also leading to new business models and innovations.

In the building and construction sector standards and building codes could become an important driver. Currently, however standards are more seen as a barrier hindering new innovative or just low-carbon products to reach the market. Please see section 6 for a review of the cement standardisation process.

2.1 Barriers and enablers

According to the work done by Jim Hart et al.¹ titled: ‘Barriers and drivers in a circular economy: the case of the built environment’, concludes that ‘Technological and regulatory developments alone will not suffice, and a shift is required in business models and stakeholder’s behaviour and attitude’.

- Some enablers are designed to target specific barriers
- Others to improve conditions for CE in generally
- Some enablers might have barriers on its own, eg. the Material passport is an enabler to address barriers concerned with recovering value from resources at the end of life, but there will be further barriers to the adoption of such a tool

Jim Hart et al. summarises their literature review into the following overview table with barriers and enablers grouped into Cultural, Regulatory, Financial and sectoral issues.

	Code	Barrier	Enabler	Link
Cultural	C1	Lack of interest, knowledge/skills and engagement throughout the value chain	Leadership	S1, S7
	C2	Operating in linear economy	Sustainability/environmental drivers	S1
	C3	Lack of vertical and horizontal collaboration	Stimulate demand	F4
	C4	Lack of collaboration between business functions – silo mentality	Value chain engagement Longer term relationships and partnerships Systems thinking	F1 F1 S2
Regulat.	R1	Lack of consistent regulatory framework	Policy support & public procurement	R1
	R2	Obstructing laws and regulations	Regulatory reform	R2
	R3	Lack of incentives for CE	Fiscal support Producer responsibility	R3 R3
Financial	F1	Short-term blinkers – CAPEX prioritised over OPEX	Whole life costing	F1, S3
	F2	High upfront investment costs.	Easy wins	F4, F2
	F3	Low virgin material prices	CBMs	F5
	F4	Poor business case / unconvincing case studies	Scale	F4
	F5	Limited funding		
Sectoral	S1	Lack of bandwidth compounded by no coherent vision	Clearer vision for CE in the built environment	S1
	S2	Complexity / confused incentives	Better evidence base	R1, F5
	S3	Long product lifecycles (buildings and materials)	Collaboration and design tools and strategies	S6, C3
	S4	Technical challenges re material recovery	R&D, innovation	S4, C1
	S5	Lacking standardization	Develop standards and assurance schemes	S5
	S6	Insufficient use or development of CE-focused design and collaboration tools, information and metrics	Develop reverse logistics infrastructure	F2, S4
	S7	The industry itself – conservative, uncollaborative, risk-averse		

Figure 2-1 Barriers and enablers towards circular economy (Source: Jim Hart et al.)

For the importance of the URBCON project and as a mean to identify policy gaps, the distinction between soft (institutional and social) and hard barriers (technological and economic) is helpful and do also to a certain extent support the evidence from IDEA study² :

What regulatory framework and/or standards would be necessary to increase or even implement the use of those types of concretes.

- ▶ Ban on landfill;
- ▶ Secondary materials should lose the “waste” status and should be given an “end-of-life” status to make them more attractive;

¹ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2212827118312940>

² Social acceptance of Eco-concrete, conducted by IDEA under the framework of the URBCON project

- ▶ *There should be made room for sustainable procurement and a reward for circularity in public tenders to create demand;*
- ▶ *There should be new standards including a broadened scope of the different types of eco-concrete, but too much regulation can block innovation;*
- ▶ *An Innovation certification for companies can be introduced;*
- ▶ *National regulations should be more aligned within the European Union so that international trade of secondary waste materials can be accelerated (e.g. discussion passports).*

Cultural barriers and enablers

Cultural barriers include social, behavioural and managerial aspects preventing transition to a circular economy. Jim Hart et al. concludes from the literature review that the following main barriers are prevailing:

- Lack of interest and engagement throughout the value chain
- Lack of collaboration between the businesses
- Lack of collaboration between business function (silo mentality)

All these aspects can also be seen as a kind of conservatism, the construction and building industry can be regarded as relatively rigid and conservative without major disruptions. The cement industry in particular is generally known as a strong lobbyist against CO2 taxation.

In such cases, usually only external pressures or drivers can trigger substantial change. The CO2 shaming of Portland Cement and the increased market demand for climate neutral products are all factors forcing the traditional building and construction industry to change. In the literature, enablers to address these barriers have been identified as Leadership, Change in demand patterns, Value chain engagement and Systems thinking.

Policy gaps: more could be done to encourage the mindset of all stakeholders along the value chain to stimulate the uptake of circularity thinking.

Potential measures: case studies, innovation projects, knowledge sharing, education.

Regulatory barriers and enablers

Regulatory barriers were identified (Jim Hart et al.) to include 'lack of consistent regulatory frameworks' and 'obstructing laws and regulations'. These barriers can already be conformed in the context of the URBCON project where the given cement standards and building codes can be said to obstruct the uptake of greener and more sustainable types of cement and concrete. This topic is further elaborated in Section 6.

Regulatory enablers that might help overcome the given barriers are identified as Public procurement, Regulatory reforms and other incentives schemes such as VAT reduction.

In the URBCON project, Public Procurement is being tested as part of the three Pilots. Lesson learnt from this Process will be reported in WP LT, Task 1.2.

Policy gaps: incentives schemes to promote testing and showcasing innovative materials

Potential measures: Reform cement standards towards performance-based regulation as opposed to OPC content

Financial/economic barriers and enablers

According to the work of Jim Hart et al. financial barriers includes issues like High upfront investment costs and in this category particular certification and compliance process costs; low virgin material costs and low EoL (End of Life) values due to the relatively long life expectancy associated with building and construction materials or structures. Poor business cases and unconvincing case studies are also mentioned as a barrier as well as limited funding, assumable related to testing of new products. Possible enablers to overcome such financial or economic barriers includes introduction of tools like 'Whole Life Costing', 'take the easy wins' (meaning going for the low hanging fruits, e.g. where the costs savings of the CE solution is evident), Circular Business Models and scaling.

Policy gaps: , lack of economic incentives, lack of compulsory LCA or CO2 footprint requirement at product and service level.

Potential measures: Promotion of Green building certification schemes including LCA/ thinking and CO2 footprints.

Sectoral barriers and enablers

Sectoral barriers refer to barriers that are unique or specific for the built environment. Again, citing Jim Hart et al., what they found during their literature review was: lack of bandwidth and no coherent vision (probably the word 'bandwidth' here could be understood as 'narrow sighted'); complexity of building and long life cycles; technical challenges regarding material recovery; lack of standardization for recycled materials; lack of ECO design, and again the lack of willingness to change/conservatism of the sector is mentioned.

Potential enablers are suggested as: better evidence base; a clear CE vision for the built environment; collaboration and tools such as Materials databases/material passport/knowledge gateways/BIM/BAMB; R&D innovation; development of standards.

Policy gaps of relevance for URBCON:

Potential measures:

2.2 Social acceptance of Eco-concrete

Under the framework of the URBCON project, a study was commissioned to investigate the Social Acceptance of Eco-concrete. The study took place during 2020 by IDEA and involved a broad stakeholder consultation from mainly Belgium, Holland and Germany.

The main findings are briefly summarised in the following.

Main reasons for using Eco-concrete:

- sustainability,
- to improve the green image

Reluctance to adapt eco-concrete:

- lack of knowledge,
- more difficult to use

The stakeholders were also asked for their opinion about some of the enablers promoted by the URBCON project, the responses are summarised below.

Enablers as promoted by URBCON	Feedback from the stakeholders
Material Passport	<p>But it might not be enough to favour the development of eco concrete on the market. Indeed, as it is not always regulated by law in the European Union, a passport is not equivalent to a working permit.</p> <p>Therefore, this leverage is not sufficient to access easily different national markets for international players and more compulsory administrative steps need to be taken by the actors.</p> <p>In addition, construction waste that serves as an input to produce eco concrete is often a mixture. Therefore, a passport is not only limited to eco concrete, but the chain of certification and identification of characteristics must include also wastes as raw materials. This approach makes it more complex to deploy a material passport for eco concrete.</p> <p>More generally, the real need is identified by some actors for a material passport at the building level.</p>
Digital Market platform for secondary raw materials	<p>67% of our sample thinks that a trading website is interesting for their company or organization.</p> <p>During the workshop there was also a universal agreement on the use of a trading website, but the organization also identified the need for materials passports in that regard. Because regulatories regarding composition of materials differ across member states, it is important that materials are described in detail to identify underlying components and so it is known to potential customers that national regulatory conditions are met. This is especially important for international operating platforms.</p> <p>Furthermore, the experience of some participants was that these platforms often contain the least interesting materials, or those of very poor quality. Frequently, the financially most interesting solution are already found via the company's own channels or bilateral connections. Therefore, the platforms are often used as a last resort for the least interesting or least feasible materials.</p> <p>Finally, the question arose if a new platform should be developed or synergies with current platforms could provide a fruitful alternative. OVAM, for example, created their Smart Symbiose, which is enlarging towards textile and lumber and is active on the European level. They showed interest to adapt their platform to the needs of the construction sector to accelerate the use of raw materials. OVAM is open to exchange with interested organization and companies.</p> <p>With the right regulatory framework, a good description of material components and policies to seduce companies to use the platform instead of searching within their own network. These platforms can function as a gamechanger to accelerate the green transition.</p>

The main recommendations from the stakeholders involved in the IDEA study are provided below:

1. Increase the knowledge of the product among stakeholders.

- ▶ There is clearly an underused market potential due to a lack of information. Not every respondent in our sample was aware of eco-concrete. Therefore, there is an important role for URBCON, governments and the sector to inform not only about the existence of eco-concrete, but also where to find them and on the different components of the different types, materialized in material passports.
- ▶ Partnerships can provide a key role in shaping coalitions to lobby for changes in the regulatory framework, but they can also play a pivot role in informing the public and the market of eco-concrete and everything related. During our study we have often engaged with researchers, platforms, or companies in the field, which were positively surprised by the URBCON project and her ambitions. Partnerships can also accelerate the green transition by sharing existing structures instead of reinventing the wheel.

2. Make second life raw material a standard of quality and change the global image of eco-concrete.

- ▶ Today, users will consider second life materials as less qualitative as raw materials. It is technically wrong. Second life materials can have better characteristics than raw materials. This perception needs to be influenced through pilot programs, demonstrators, and communication
- ▶ A campaign should be developed so that secondary materials can shake off their “waste status”. and make them more attractive. This could be a public-private cooperation, as national governments are to accelerate the green transition.
- ▶ An Innovation certification can be introduced for companies using or producing eco-concrete.

3. Align the regulatory framework and use green procurement as tool to scale up.

- ▶ National regulations across member states should be more aligned so that international trade of secondary waste materials can be accelerated. Specifically, to ban environmentally degrading processes and the international approval of nationally used types and forms of eco-concrete. This is especially important to accelerate “renovation wave” formulated in the Green Deal by the European Commission.
- ▶ National regulations should allow more types of eco-concrete on the market, without specifying the material components in too much detail so that innovation is not blocked. This limits the entry of new materials or new businesses, due to high costs that are to be made in advance to “prove” that materials are in line with government regulation). If national regulations across member states are more aligned this could significantly decrease the costs of the eco-concrete and enhance its scalability.
- ▶ Public tenders are key to develop circularity of products, specifically eco concrete. There should be made room for sustainable procurement and a reward for circularity in public tenders to create demand for eco-concrete, secondary raw materials or environment enhancing products and processes.

4. Strengthen financial support to pilot programs.

- ▶ This is especially important in relation to the cost gap between non-sustainable and sustainable processes as described above. Financial sanctions on environmental degrading processes could limit the unnecessary use of primary materials. This could also decrease the cost gap between secondary raw materials and primary raw materials, if not make this obsolete. It could be formalised by a carbon tax for European market. This mechanism is a key factor success for deployment of eco-concrete.

3 Overview of relevant EU Policies

In 2016, during the UN climate summit in Paris, it was agreed among nearly 200 countries to limit global warming to a maximum of 2° Celsius and pursue efforts to 1.5°. In order to distribute the implications of the agreement fairly, the contribution for each country has been distributed accordingly.

The countries in the European Union have agreed to a reduction target of 40% CO² in 2030 and 80-95% CO² in 2050. The reduction targets are based on the emission levels of 1990.

The European policies on climate and circular economy are actively in development at the time of writing. As a result, increasingly elaborated plans are developed to implement and achieve the objectives, such as action plans and laws and regulations. Most of these documents are in preparation and will await for approval in the coming months / years.

3.1 Climate

The basis of the European policy on climate is The European Green Deal (2019). The Green Deal is the roadmap of European policy for the period of 2019 – 2024. As part of the Green Deal, action plans and strategies are developed to elaborate on specific themes, such as renewable energy, circular economy, biodiversity and sectoral strategies.

The EU strives for a maximum warming of 1.5 degrees, to which end it is estimated the world should be climate neutral by 2050. Therefore, the main target of The EU Green Deal's is to make Europe a climate neutral continent by 2050. In October 2020 the EU voted with approval to the European Climate Law. The law is forwarded to the EU Council of Ministers for final approval. When approved the following targets will become mandatory:

- Increase from 40% to 50 – 60 % reduction of CO² emission by 2030 compared to 1990
- All European countries are climate neutral in 2050

Figure 3-1. Greenhouse gas emissions trend projections and target (EEA, 2019) <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/figures/greenhouse-gas-emission-trend-projections>

Relevant documents:

- The European Green Deal - European Commission (2019)
- European Climate Law (2020)
- 2030 Climate Target Plan

Stepping up Europe’s 2030 climate ambition investing in a climate-neutral future for the benefit of our people (2020) - https://ec.europa.eu/clima/sites/clima/files/eu-climate-action/docs/impact_en.pdf

Figure 3-2. A pathway to climate neutrality

The sectors contributing the most to the greenhouse gas emissions are Energy, Industry and Transport. Especially the energy sector has priority in policy making, as can be seen in figure xx. Surprisingly no national policies on (circular) use of resources are highlighted in the overview.

Figure ES.3 Reported expected savings from national policies linked to key EU policies 2030.

Note: Only EU28 countries included, for Austria and Romania reported information of 2017 was used.
Source: ETC/CME, 2019.

Construction / Concrete:

The Strategy for a Sustainable Built Environment is in development, which follows the targets of the Green Deal and Climate Law. In addition, it will address the following aspect for climate neutrality:

- The sustainability performance of construction products in the context of revising the Construction Product Regulation (CPR);
- Integrated Life Cycle Assessment in public procurement.

3.2 Circular Economy

Since half of the CO² emissions are caused by extraction and processing of resources, achieving the climate targets is not possible without the transition to a fully circular economy. Therefore, circular economy is one of the main topics of the Green Deal to achieve the climate goals.

Targets:

Specific targets for circular economy are to be developed, however based on the climate targets, the economy needs to be fully circular in 2050. To achieve this goal the system needs to be deeply transformed. Essential for this transition is to rethink the design of products for reuse and recyclability and the promotion of circularity in industrial processes.

- Make sustainable products the norm in the EU;
- Empower consumers and public buyers;
- Focus on the sectors that use most resources and where the potential for circularity is high such as: electronics and ICT; batteries and vehicles; packaging; plastics; textiles; construction and buildings; food; water and nutrients;

- Ensure less waste;
- Make circularity work for people, regions and cities,
- Lead global efforts on circular economy.

Relevant documents:

- Closing the loop - An EU action plan for the Circular Economy - European Commission (2015)
- A new Circular Economy Action Plan - For a cleaner and more competitive Europe - European Commission (2020)

Construction / Concrete:

The strategy for a Sustainable Built Environment is in development. This strategy will ensure coherence among relevant policy areas such as climate, energy and resource efficiency. In terms of Circular Economy, it will address:

- Introduction of recycled content requirements;
- Improvement of durability and adaptability and development of digital logbooks of buildings;
- Material recovery targets for construction and demolition waste, aiming for no waste to landfill;

The renovation wave initiative aims to improve energy efficiency and implementation of circular economy principles to optimize and extend the lifecycle of current building stock.

- Renovation Wave - A Renovation Wave for Europe (October, 2020)

4 Policies implemented at National and Regional Level

Overview of reported national policies and measures on climate change mitigation in Europe in 2019

Figure ES.1 Total number of existing and planned policies and measures reported in the EU-28 (left) and by countries (right).

Notes: *2017 reporting, ** non-EU countries
Source: ETC/CME, 2019.

Figure 4-1. Timeline of Circular Economy developments in other European countries (Source: Thomas Weber & Martin Stuchtey, 2019)

"The investigated country strategies describe a CE as an approach to achieving and harmonizing existing national targets which have already been set in various policy areas, most frequently targets

for recycling rates, waste volumes and CO2 emissions. Moreover, other than in the Netherlands, no additional national circularity targets has been defined.”

4.1 The Netherlands

4.1.1 Climate

The government takes measures to protect the Netherlands against the consequences of climate change. In addition, further global warming can be mitigated by reducing greenhouse gas emissions. National and international agreements have been made for achieving targets.

Figure 4-2. Emissions in the Netherlands in megatons for 2017 (Voorstel voor het Klimaatplan, Ministerie van Economische Zaken en Klimaat, 2019)

Targets:

- 25% less CO2 emissions in 2020 compared to 1990
- 49% less CO2 emissions in 2030 compared to 1990
- 95% less CO2 emissions in 2050 compared to 1990

Relevant document:

National and international agreements:

- United Nations (UN) Climate Change Convention, 1992.
- Kyoto Protocol, 1997.
- UN climate summit in Paris: the Conference of Parties (COP21), 2016.
- The Dutch Climate Act, 2019.

“The judge determined the call for a Dutch climate act as result of a lawsuit in 2015 against the Dutch State. The judgment was confirmed in the appeal of 2018 and 2019, making the judgement irrevocable. As a result the target of 25% less CO2 emissions in 2020 compared to 1990 is mandatory. In addition, the climate act states that a climate plan needs to be drafted.”

[Climate plan](#)

The first proposal for a climate plan is presented in the autumn of 2019 and applies for the period between 2021 and 2030. This plan contains:

- the main features of the policy with which the Cabinet wishes to achieve the objectives of the Climate Act;
- a number of reflections, for example on the latest scientific insights into climate change and the economic consequences of the policy.

Construction / Concrete:

Voorstel voor klimaatplan p.23 – Built environment

The goal for the built environment is to emit 3.4 Mton less CO₂ by 2030 than in the reference scenario. In order to achieve the target, approximately 1.5 million existing homes must be made more sustainable and CO₂ emissions in existing non-residential buildings must be reduced by an additional 1 Mton by 2030. Main strategies are focused on energy efficiency through renovation and disconnection of natural gas usage for heating and cooking.

MPG – Milieu Prestatie Gebouwen / Environmental Performance of Buildings

The Environmental Performance of Buildings (MPG) is mandatory for every application for an environmental permit. The MPG indicates the environmental impact of the materials used in a building. This concerns new office buildings (larger than 100 m²) and new-build homes. As of 1 January 2018, a maximum limit value of 1.0 applies to the MPG.

The MPG is an important measure of the sustainability of a building. The lower the MPG, the more sustainable the use of materials. The MPG is an objective tool in the design process, and it can be used in a Schedule of Requirements to record the result of a design process.

MKI (Milieu Kosten Indicator) / ECI (Environmental Costs Indicator)

LCAs and MKI/ECI are mainly taking off in the Dutch construction sector. The results of the life cycle analysis (LCA), such as the MKI/ECI value, are increasingly being requested in tenders. In some tenders, the score is used as the main criterion to determine the winning bid.

Tenderers can obtain a fictitious discount on their offer with the MKI value.

Figure 4-3. Calculation of the MKI/ECI value in 4 steps, based on the LCA (EcoCahin, Luc Hillege)

4.1.2 Circular Economy

In the national program ‘[Nederland Circulair in 2050](#)’ the transformation of the economy into a sustainable, fully circular economy is outlined. The program describes what is required to use raw materials, products and services more efficiently and smarter. The goal: The Netherlands to be fully circular by 2050.

Figure 4-4. Elements of a circular economy - <https://themasites.pbl.nl/o/circular-economy/>

Figure 4-5. Benefits of the circular economy for the Netherlands – TNO, adaptation by PBL

Targets:

1. Increased efficient use of raw materials within the production processes to reduce the usage of raw materials.
2. When new raw materials are needed, these are made as much as possible of sustainable produced, renewable (inexhaustible) and generally available raw materials, like biomass. This makes the Netherlands less dependent on fossil sources and it is better for the environment.
3. Development of circular production methods and circular design of new products.

Relevant documents:

Grondstoffenakkoord – Raw Materials Agreement:

In January 2017, 180 parties in The Hague signed the '[Grondstoffenakkoord](#)'. This document is an agreement between government and business parties towards a Dutch circular economy based on reusable raw materials.

Transition agenda's:

In 2018 the Dutch national government made 5 transition agenda's together with the parties of the '[Grondstoffenakkoord](#)'. The agenda's are composed for the most important sectors in terms of economics and environmental impact:

- [Biomass and food](#)
- [Plastics](#)
- [Manufacturing industry](#)
- [Construction sector](#)
- [Consumer goods](#)

Implementation program 2019 – 2023

In 2019 the ‘[Uitvoeringsprogramma Circulaire Economie](#)’ is presented. This program translates the transition agenda’s into actions and a project for the period of 2019 – 2023. The program will be regularly reviewed; annually there will be a National Conference to discuss on the progress; every two years the national Environmental Assessment Agency (PBL) will monitor the progress in a report; every five years the national government updates the program.

Construction / Concrete:

Transition agenda construction sector

Betonakkoord – Concrete Agreement

The concrete agreement focusses on 7 themes, such as CO²-reduction, circular design, reuse of concrete waste and decrease of MKI (Environmental Cost Indicator: the Dutch indicator of a LCA-study). For CO²-reduction the agreement follows the national target to reduce CO² emissions by 49% in 2030.

In addition, concrete waste from demolition needs to be 100% reused in production of new concrete by 2030. This would result in a reduction of 15 – 20% primary resource usage, since the demand for construction is higher than supply from demolition.

Tabel 1. Recycling targets of concrete demolition waste (Concrete Agreement)

Reusable Materials	2020	2025	2030
Gravel	50%	75%	100%
Sand	10%	50%	100%
Binder / Filler	1%	25%	100%
Reusable Materials	2020	2025	2030

4.2 Belgium

4.2.1 Climate

The federal government of Belgium focusses on the reduction goal of the greenhouse gas emissions, coming from the international Paris agreements and European commitments. Those are written down in the [federal contribution](#) to the [national energy- and climate plan](#) 2021-2030 and have been approved by the federal government on the 29th of November 2019. A long term strategy (2050) was finished in February 2020. The Federal state in 2013 already strived for a reduction of the emissions of greenhouse gasses on Belgian soil with at least 80-95% by 2050 compared to 1990.

Targets:

- 35% reduction of greenhouse gas emissions in 2030 compared to 2005
- 80-95% reduction of greenhouse gas emissions in 2050 compared to 1990

Relevant documents:

<https://www.nationaalenergieklimaatplan.be/admin/storage/nekp/nekp-deel-a.pdf>

Construction / Concrete:

4.2.2 Circular Economy

The federal government of Belgium has written down 21 measures to promote the transition to circular economy.

Targets:

Belgian companies are worldwide known for their innovative recycling techniques, for the usage of secondary or renewable resources and the collection of waste. By that, they have developed a knowhow that has a high added value, which gives them access to new markets. Belgium could expand the collection of waste to the surrounding countries and for that valorize a bigger amount of new resources, for which the knowhow will be an important valorization criterium. The strategic and central position in Europe, with a market of 60 to 80 million consumers, offers the logistic sector a real chance of being active in all the phases of the product lifecycle.

Last but not least, Belgium has a tight bond with the European institutions and can play an important role as initiator on an European level.

Relevant documents:

https://www.health.belgium.be/sites/default/files/uploads/fields/fpshealth_theme_file/circ-econ-nl-light.pdf (English version not working, only French and Dutch available)

Construction / Concrete:

No specific targets/measures for the construction area.

4.3 Flanders

4.3.1 Climate

On the 9th of December 2019 the Flemish government approved the Flemish Energy and Climate plan 2021-2030.

Targets:

Flanders strives to reduce the greenhouse gas emissions on non-ETS sectors with 35% by 2030 compared to 2005.

Relevant documents:

<https://omgeving.vlaanderen.be/sites/default/files/atoms/files/VR%202019%200912%20DOC.1208-3%20VEKP%2021-30%20-%20bijlageBIS.pdf>

Construction / Concrete:

The Flemish government wishes to reach this goal by amongst others:

- Further innovation, e.g. by digitalising the building sector;
- Sooner implementing the circular economy under the impulse of additional initiatives of and with the business world, like circular building
- Stimulating renovation of residential buildings after sale and compelling it with non-residential building after sale.
- Stimulation rebuilding after demolition

4.3.2 Circular Economy

Since the first of January 2017 the three pillars of the former Flemish Materials Program (plan C, SuMMa and Agenda 2020) continue to work under the name of '[Circular Flanders](#)'. They work on three pillars:

- Circular purchasing
- Circular city
- Circular businesses

And on five themes:

- Materials
- Biomass
- Water
- Space
- Energy

The starting note for the transition priority 'carry on the transition to a circular economy' has been approved on the 24th of 2017 by the Flemish government. There are seven transition priorities, mentioned in the note Vision2050, which sets out the long term strategy for Flanders, approved in March 2016. These transitions are structural changes that have a huge impact on the society.

Circular Flanders states in the vision that the Flanders region is circular in 2050.

Relevant documents:

file:///C:/Users/HabetsSa/Downloads/Startnota_transitieprioriteit_transitie_naar_de_circulaire_economie_doorzetten_bijlage.pdf

Construction / Concrete:

At the start of 2019 Circular Flanders, OVAM (the Public Waste Agency of Flanders) and the Flemish Building Confederation launched the Green Deal Circular Building. In this engagement, 320 organisations are working together to make circular building in Flanders a daily reality. To participate, organisations need to:

1. Execute at least one pilot project during the duration of the Green Deal
2. Actively participate to the learning network in which knowledge and experiences will be shared
3. Agree to the researchers having access to all relevant data, results and lessons learned from the pilots
4. Take steps to implement the principles of circular building structurally in their own organisation

The City of Ghent is part of the Green Deal Circular Building.

4.4 Germany

4.4.1 Climate

The Climate Action Plan 2050 outlines a modernisation strategy for the necessary transformation towards a low-carbon economy in Germany on three levels:

- *It contains specific guiding principles for the individual areas of action for 2050, leaving scope for innovations and striving to maximize sustainability.*
- *It outlines robust transformation pathways for all areas of action, highlights critical path dependencies and describes interdependencies.*
- *It underpins goals, in particular the interim GHG target for 2030 of at least a 55 percent reduction in GHG emissions compared to 1990, with emission targets for all sectors, concrete milestones and strategic measures, also taking impact and cost analyses into account.*

Sectoral targets in the Climate Action Plan 2050

The sector targets are shown in 2030 from the Climate Protection Plan 2050 (in millions of tonnes of CO₂ equivalents)

Source: Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation and Nuclear Safety (2017). Climate protection in figures 2017

Figure 14: Greenhouse gas emission trends and determined annual targets by sector

Further information on greenhouse gas emission trends and the determined annual targets by sector can be found in the data appendix on page 66.

Sources: UBA (2020a), UBA (2020b), Federal Government (2019)

Relevant documents:

- Climate Action Plan 2050 – Germany's long-term low greenhouse gas emission development strategy
- Federal Climate Change Act (2019)
- Facts, Trends and Incentives for German Climate Policy 2020 edition

Construction / Concrete:

Annual emission budgets in millions of tonnes of CO ₂ equivalent	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030
Energy	280		257								175
Industry	186	182	177	172	168	163	158	154	149	145	140
Buildings	118	113	108	103	99	94	89	84	80	75	70
Transport	150	145	139	134	128	123	117	112	106	101	95
Agriculture	70	68	67	66	65	64	63	61	60	59	58
Waste and Other	9	9	8	8	7	7	7	6	6	5	5

Figure 4-6. Permissible annual emission budgets (Federal Climate Change Act, 2019)

4.4.2 Circular Economy

“In Germany, there is no overarching strategy on how a Circular Economy can be achieved although Germany considerably shaped the debate at the international level. Germany is a driver of innovation and with its technical infrastructure is excellently positioned to drive this change. On the political side there are already various strategies, platforms and initiatives that address elements of the Circular Economy narrative. Those are, however, not yet aligned to one overall strategy.” - <https://www.circular-economy-initiative.de/english>

The *Circular Economy Initiative Deutschland* brings together economic, scientific and societal stakeholders. Its aim is to develop a joint target vision and a concrete plan on how the transformation towards a Circular Economy in Germany could be fostered. On top, the initiative seeks to initiate practical implementation, for example in the form of collaborative projects. In summary, the insights from the initiative serve as a basis for deriving policy recommendations and options which are summarized in a Circular Economy Roadmap for Germany.

Targets:

- **An explicit implementation strategy is essential for achieving targets:** German policy makers have already developed a target system through Agenda 2030, national CO₂ targets, the raw material productivity target from ProgRes and the National Sustainable Development Strategy, the targets in the Hightech-Strategy 2025 etc. which a CE strategy can help with achieving. An explicit CE strategy would therefore be of additional benefit to Germany by supporting and driving forward integrated implementation of the existing targets.
- **The indicator set for measuring progress must be expanded:** In order to make the progress towards CE measurable, Germany would have to develop a comprehensive system of indicators going beyond the efficiency concept (see explanations about indicators, page 30 ff.). One important factor here is that macroeconomic models can only deliver relevant insights if the indicators can also be applied at an operational level in order to inform processes in businesses.
- **A hierarchy of targets can avoid conflicts during implementation:** Interviews with experts revealed that developing a hierarchy of targets would be advantageous in relation to possible trade-offs (e.g. climate protection versus independence from critical material imports).

Relevant documents:

Weber, T., Stuchtey, M., Kadner, S., Schweitzer, K., Buttkeireit, S., Marm, A., ... & Wolf, R. (2019). Pathways towards a German Circular Economy. Lessons from European Strategies Preliminary Study.

Circular Business Models: Overcoming Barriers, Unleashing Potentials

Lah, O. (2016), ‘Circular Economy Policies and Strategies of Germany’, in Anbumozhi, V. and J. Kim (eds.), *Towards a Circular Economy: Corporate Management and Policy Pathways*. ERIA Research Project Report 2014-44, Jakarta: ERIA, pp.59-74.

4.5 United Kingdom

4.5.1 Climate

The United Kingdom was the first nation to legally commit to the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions. In 2008 The Climate Change Act was accepted, setting the reduction target to at least 80% by 2050. In 2019 a regulatory order increased the target to achieve net zero emissions (100%) by 2050.

UK - Total emissions of greenhouse gases, 1990-2018

IfG

Source: Institute for Government analysis of: *Final UK greenhouse gas emissions national statistics*, BEIS, February 2020

CC BY-NC

UK - Emissions by sector, 1990-2018

IfG

Source: Institute for Government analysis of: *Final UK greenhouse gas emissions national statistics*, BEIS, February 2020
 Note: Net negative emissions from LULUCF not shown.

CC BY-NC

Targets:

The main goal of the UK policies is achieving a net-zero emission by 2050.

Relevant documents:

- Climate Change Act 2008
- The Clean Growth Strategy and Clean Growth Grand Challenge, 2017
- The 25 Year Environment Plan, 2018
- Climate change: second national adaptation programme (2018 to 2023), 2018
- UK National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP), 2019
- Climate Change Act 2008 (2050 Target Amendment) Order 2019

Carbon Budgets

The Climate Change Act 2008 requires the government to set five yearly carbon budgets, that will run until 2032. The budgets are fixed in advance and set five-year caps on the total greenhouse gas emissions allowed to ensure the UK meets its emissions reductions commitments.

Construction / Concrete:

The government and the construction sector, through the Construction Leadership Council, have agreed a Sector Deal to transform the productivity of the sector benefiting the wider economy.

The deal will substantially boost the sector's productivity, through greater investment in innovation and skills, creating new and well-paid jobs and maximizing its export potential. This will also reduce the environmental impact, improve the efficiency and reduce whole life cost of new projects and buildings to help build the houses, schools, hospitals and major transport projects.

4.5.2 Circular Economy

Targets:

The strategy is framed by natural capital thinking and guided by **two overarching Objectives:**

1. To maximise the value of resource use;
2. To minimise waste and its impact on the environment.

The strategy contributes to the delivery of **five strategic ambitions:**

1. all plastic packaging placed on the market being recyclable, reusable or compostable by 2025;
2. eliminating food waste to landfill by 2030;
3. eliminate avoidable³ plastic waste over the lifetime of the 25 Year Environment Plan;
4. double resource productivity⁴ by 2050;
5. eliminate avoidable waste of all kinds by 2050.

Relevant documents:

- Circular Economy Package (CEP), 2020
- OUR WASTE, OUR RESOURCES: A STRATEGY FOR ENGLAND (2018)

³ plastic waste being 'avoidable' when the plastic could have been reused or recycled; when a reusable or recyclable alternative could have been used instead; or when it could have been composted or biodegraded in the open environment.

⁴ Resource productivity is a measure of the value (in terms of GDP) we generate per unit of raw materials we use in the economy.

Construction / Concrete:

What are likely to be the challenges for CE thinking in the built environment?

Much of the work to develop CE thinking to date has been focused on short-lived consumer goods such as phones, computers, washing machines etc. But can this thinking also be applied to buildings and infrastructure that exist for decades if not centuries. Examples of the reuse of buildings or construction materials and products litter the millennia, but how can modern buildings and modern materials be designed to be better used, last longer and be available for similar or alternate purposes at end of life. The challenges for adapting CE thinking in construction are likely to be complex and include:

Products, buildings and infrastructure:

- Long life of buildings, infrastructure and products.
- Complexity of buildings.
- Variable lifespans of components of buildings.
- Existing, especially more recent, buildings are not designed for today's End of Life issues.
- Changes in specification and technology over time mean that many products may become redundant in future.

Recovery of products/materials:

- Often a low commercial value of materials/ products (apart from metals) at demolition.
- Lack of widespread secondary market mechanisms.

- Lack of quality assurance for secondary and recycled materials.
- Problematic logistics of moving and storing materials.
- Constraints of existing waste legislation.
- Complex materials and products which are increasing in use can be difficult to reuse.
- Viability of extended user responsibility requirements for long-lived buildings and products
- Changes in legislation may mean that recovered material no longer complies with certain regulations e.g. REACH.

Business considerations:

- Value of adopting CE practices.
- Use of discount rates can effectively mean the value of recovered materials in 20 years' time can be zero.
- Most companies will build in depreciation so the value of products in the future are written off.
- Viable business models e.g. leasing products as a service may only be relevant to short-lived products such as lights and carpet tiles.
- Ownership of resources (IP), testing, warranties, guarantees etc of reused, reclaimed products.

Other considerations:

- Understanding life cycle thinking to aid complex decisions, e.g. delivering lower carbon in performance but creating end of life issues? Or the opposite, creating good end of life possibilities but increasing carbon emissions in the process.
- A potential disconnect between developer and constructor, freeholder or leaseholder and occupant make keeping track and benefiting from CE over a building lifecycle difficult.
- Applying systems thinking (i.e. the whole supply chain working together).
- Measuring circularity for complex long-lived buildings and infrastructure made of multiple products and materials.
- Information management and data needs – what information is needed, when is it needed to make informed decisions, who needs this information and in what format.
- Engaging SME businesses.

Figure 4-7.

The construction industry is on the brink of fundamental change with developments such as digitalisation, off-site manufacturing and new, innovative construction materials and techniques offering huge potential for increasing resource efficiency. The recently announced Construction Sector Deal recognises this and will deliver an investment of up to £420 million between industry and Government to accelerate this transformation. The focus on transforming construction through use of digital building design and new manufacturing technologies offers a unique opportunity to reduce waste and increase productivity, with an overall aim of a 50% reduction in build time.

In addition, The Green Construction Board⁵ has developed guidance for increasing resource efficiency and reducing waste in the sector through the adoption of circular economy principles. We will work with them to establish a definition of zero avoidable waste in the sector and develop an ambitious route map by 2020 setting out how and when this can be achieved.

⁵ Green Construction Board (2018)

<https://www.greenconstructionboard.org/index.php/resources/circular-economy>

5 Policies implemented at City level

5.1 Rotterdam

The objectives of Rotterdam can be divided into four ambitions:

1. Energy transition
2. Transition to a circular economy
3. Climate-proof environment
4. Healthy environment

Rotterdam strives to connect these ambitions as much as possible, so that they strengthen each other in the implementation. For this policy review the focus areas are the energy transition and circularity.

5.1.1 Climate

Since Rotterdam is accountable for 20% of the national CO₂-emissions, the climate goals of the Paris agreement are integrated in the Rotterdam policies.

Targets:

- In 2022 the annual CO₂ emissions show a downward trend
- In 2030 the CO₂ emissions are 49% reduced compared to 1990
- In 2050 Rotterdam is climate neutral

Relevant documents:

- *Duurzaamheidskompas. Gemeente Rotterdam (2019)*
- *Woonvisie; woningbouwakkoord 2018 – 2021*
- *Visie Openbare Ruimte 2019 – 2029*
- *Rotterdams Klimaatakkoord*

5.1.2 Circular Economy

Circular economy and circularity are concepts that are used interchangeably. Circularity is the technique and logistics for closing cycles, while circular economy is the underlying economic system for circularity: the driver to make circularity financially attractive for consumers and companies. According to Rotterdam the basis for a circular economy consists of:

- Prevention and reduction of use of primary raw materials;
- Extending the lifespan of products;
- Reuse of products and components;
- Recycling of products into raw materials.

Targets:

- 40 new circular initiatives in 2023
- 50% reduction of primary raw materials in 2030
- 3.500 – 7.000 additional circular jobs in 2030
- In 2050 Rotterdam will be completely circular: Material cycles are closed.

Figure 5-2. Environmental impact analysis comparison of different materials (Metabolic, 2018)

5.2 City of Ghent

5.2.1 Climate

The city of Ghent has a Climate Plan 2020-2025. This has more than 100 action points in 7 different domains: energy-efficient living, renewable energy, companies and the tertiary sector, nutrition, transportation, circular economy and climate adaptation.

Gent Klimaatstad

Samen met Gentenaars, organisaties, bedrijven en scholen maken we van Gent een Klimaatstad.

ENERGIEZUINIG WONEN

- 1 Gentse woningen verbruiken 30 % minder energie in 2030
- 2 De Stad helpt Gentenaars om woningen goed te isoleren en hernieuwbare energie gebruiken

BEDRIJVEN

- 7 Stad Gent begeleidt Gentse ondernemers die hun gebouwen energiezuinig maken en hernieuwbare energie gebruiken
- 8 De Stad Gent bespaart jaarlijks 3 % energie op eigen gebouwen
- 9 Klimaatneutrale haven

TRANSPORT

- 10 Minder autoverplaatsingen, meer verplaatsingen met openbaar vervoer, fiets, te voet
- 11 Gent investeert in duurzame stadsdistributie
- 12 De Stad investeert in elektrisch rijden en auto delen

VOEDING

Samen met de Voedselraad verduurzamt de Stad het Gentse voedselsysteem verder:

- 15 Gentenaars eten meer plantaardig
- 16 Gentenaars kopen meer korte keten
- 17 Minder eten belandt in de vuilbak

HERNIEUWBARE ENERGIE

- 3 Verdubbeling zonnepanelen tegen 2025
- 4 +100 MW windenergie tegen 2030
- 5 Gasloos verwarmen tegen 2050
- 6 Uitbreiden warmtenetten

CIRCULAIRE ECONOMIE

- 13 Kleinschalige circulaire initiatieven in Gent versterken
- 14 Circulaire economie opschalen samen met de Cleantech Cluster Regio Gent

KLIMAATADAPTATIE

Gent aanpassen aan hitte, droogte, hevige regen

- 18 Minder voorharding
- 19 Meer groen
- 20 Hergebruik en infiltratie regenwater

Gent aanpassen aan klimaatverandering

-40 % CO₂

Targets:

The goal is to reduce our CO2 emissions with at least 40% by 2030 compared to 2007. In the long run (2050) the City of Ghent wants to become a climate neutral city – meaning no net CO2 emissions.

Relevant documents:

<https://stad.gent/sites/default/files/media/documents/Klimaatplan%20Gent%202020-2025.pdf>

Construction/concrete:

Ghent stimulates and guides energy-efficient interventions in existing and new housing. Actions can be found in the Climate Plan.

For circular economy, the City of Ghent targets on sectors that have a big impact on energy usage and CO2-emissions, like building materials and plastics. On the 18th of May 2016 the Cleantech Cluster Ghent Region was founded, in which the city together with North Sea Port, Ghent University, Province of East-Flanders, POM East-Flanders and Cleantech Flanders works towards a resilient cleantech-ecosystem in the Ghent region. There has been a flow and value chain analysis on building materials, out of which two specific projects originated (URBCON and [Stapsteen](#)). By the Cleantech Cluster Ghent, the city builds towards a cleantech ecosystem.

Within the own organisation, circular procurement and circular building finds their place. A heritage framework will be set up, to implement the circular principles.

5.2.2 Circular economy

The transition towards a circular economy is one of the 7 domains of importance in the Ghent Climate Plan 2020-2025.

Also in the policy note of the economy department, more specific under the spearhead ‘Cleantech’ and mentioned in the section regarding usage of public space and the development/reconversion of old, abandoned industrial sites and newly developed business parks.

There is a separate chapter on North Sea Port. The city challenges the harbour to be a sustainable port, amongst others in the field of circular economy.

Targets:

In the Climate Plan, the goal is to reduce the footprint of the city and of North Sea Port by reducing the use of primary raw materials and keeping materials and products longer in the value chain. The City of Ghent will take an exemplary role in her internal operations and will stimulate or support other actors. We wish to take on a pioneering role in Europe.

City of Ghent wishes to take the position of pioneer in Europe in the field of circular economy and by experimenting and co-creating around maximising the reuse of products and raw materials and minimising value destruction.

Relevant documents:

<https://stad.gent/sites/default/files/media/documents/Beleidsnota%20Economie%202020-2025.pdf>

Construction/concrete:

The City of Ghent is part of the Green Deal Circular Building (see above).

5.3 Private Initiatives

There are a number of private initiatives which in one way or another are promoting the green agenda within the building and construction sector. The following list is by far complete, but the intention is to mention some private initiatives that might potentially constitute important drivers. Furthermore, we see it as a living table that can be updated on a continuous basis.

Name	Scope	Relevance for URBCON
<p><u>Green building certification schemes</u></p>	<p>There are numerous sustainability certifications for the built environment, most known are: Active House, BREEAM, DGNB, Green Star, HQE, LEED, Living Building Challenge, Miljöbyggnad, Nordic Swan and WELL. A comparison of the different schemes is available here: https://sbi.dk/Pages/Guide-to-sustainable-building-certifications.aspx</p>	<p>Increased green building certification schemes will result in higher interest for and demand for carbon neutral building materials and long term performance, although the materials itself are just one criteria in the overall certification schemes, the others being comfort/health; energy, maintenance, etc.</p>
<p><u>Pantheon Performance</u> Foundation/Platform/ Movement</p> <p>http://sustcon.org/index.php/pantheon-performance/</p>	<p>Pantheon Performance Platform aims to be an international platform for all other platforms, aiming at:</p> <p>being a common voice for sustainable building materials with governments that can promote applications and help overcome obstacles</p> <p>A "Manual of sustainable materials for CO2 neutral constructions" is underway Pantheon Performance organise internal recognised webinars on the topic</p>	<p>Although it is unsure how much influence the Pantheon Performance Foundation has on the established industry and policy makers, all pressures promoting the carbon neutral materials, performance standards etc. is indeed an important driver .</p>
<p><u>Beton Akkoord</u></p> <p>https://www.betonakkoord.nl/</p>	<p>Beton Akkoord/Concrete agreement is a private industry initiative open to all parties in the value chain encouraging collaboration for the industry to become sustainable.</p> <p>A large number of mainly Dutch players have already signed up, the type of stakeholders include: Clients (mainly public and utilities); Suppliers; Construction companies;</p>	<p>Holland is leading the way when it comes to greening the building and construction sector, hence it is likely that this initiative could spread to other parts of EU.</p>

Table 5-1 Examples of private initiatives

Figure 5-3 Factors included in different Green Building Certification Schemes (Source: Guide to Sustainable Building Certifications)

6 Standardisation, private initiatives and status on circularity

6.1 Standardisation and Regulations

The ability to use innovative concrete materials under established material and structural standards – particularly Eurocode (EN 1992) – is essential to the uptake of a new concrete at the broadest possible scale. Unfortunately, the Eurocode standards are currently prescriptive regarding the concrete constituents that can be used, cascading the requirements of EN 206 (for concrete) and thus to EN 197-1 (for cement) into the structural level. Evolution and large-scale alteration within this cascading series of standards at European level is very slow, as seen by the time taken to implement the standard that was originally published as prEN 197-1:2014, and eventually approved as EN 197-5:2021, seven years later, to add a small number of additional classes of cement to the portfolio of EN 197-1 without expanding the range of raw materials accepted for use. Some of the current delays in standardisation at a European level relate to the “Elliott case” [James Elliott Construction Limited vs Irish Asphalt Limited, 2016], which has necessitated some deep reassessment of European standards and their legal basis, and therefore delayed updates to many harmonised European standards. However, even aside from these (hopefully temporary) issues, there are structural aspects of the cascading requirements of EN standards into Eurocode, and the prescriptive nature of many of the standards for concrete and its constituents, which mean that it is likely to be difficult to bring alternative cementitious materials into this system on a footing which is directly competitive with established Portland cement-based materials, unless future releases of Eurocode are adapted significantly to draw in a wider range of material on the basis of reaching a more sustainable sector-wide emissions profile.

To demonstrate that this is possible within the scope of a major building code, it is instructive to compare with the American Concrete Institute code ACI 318, which is the main international alternative to Eurocode for concrete structural design. The 2019 release of this code, ACI 318-19, explicitly permits the use of alternative cementitious materials, which must be granted approval by both the designer and the building official, with responsibility placed on the material supplier and concrete producer to conduct sufficient testing to demonstrate sufficient technical performance of the material in conditions resembling the intended application. The materials standardisation body ASTM International is also currently developing material specifications for several non-Portland cements, including alkali-activated cementitious materials, via open Work Items assigned to its technical committees, and these specifications are expected to underpin broader standards development work to incorporate more sustainable materials into a broader range of concrete applications and concrete products produced within that regulatory framework.

Moving back to the European context, national-level documents that are either applicable to a broad class of materials (e.g. the performance-based British document BSI PAS 8820:2016 for alkali-activated cementitious materials, and the concretes made from them), or national/cross-national assessments that are specific to a particular product produced by a single manufacturer (e.g. European Technical Assessments and other parallel documents, which have been granted to alkali-activated materials in key jurisdictions), can offer opportunities for acceptance (e.g. via CE marking in the case of European Technical Assessments) in the European construction products market beyond the constraints of the core EN standardisation system.

Practice and advances in other countries also offer some lessons that can be learned: in Australia, commercial-scale deployment of alkali-activated concretes has been driven largely by usage in applications where the asset-owner is either a major constructor or a government authority with the

authorisation to develop its own catalogue of materials specifications for use in projects under its control. In such instances, the end-users are able to draft material specifications that are inclusive of the innovative materials that they intend to use – which requires technical collaboration and demonstration of performance on the part of the materials supplier, and willingness from the end-user to invest time and money in amending and expanding their catalogue of specifications. However, this approach has yielded important developments and demonstration projects for alkali-activated cementitious materials, which are arguably more advanced (in terms of the scale and maturity of commercial developments) in Australia than in other nations worldwide.

6.2 Status of circular economy - how far are we and how do we measure progress

In Europe the first interest in Circular Economy (CE) leads back to before the turn of the millennium. Initially the concept emerged from the need of an improved waste management system. Over the past decade the concept of CE further developed, especially with the publication of *Towards a Circular Economy* by the Ellen MacArthur Foundation in 2013. The Ellen MacArthur framework expanded the concept from waste-oriented to a systematic approach, taking the whole lifecycle of resources into account.

In terms of policies, CE was embraced by Europe with the CE Package in 2015, after which member states followed with national and local strategy documents. While the European CE package contributed to creating a common understanding of CE, the reviewed national and local CE strategies varies in focus area and priority. The cohesive understanding is that CE provides benefits for the economy (Weber & Stuchtey, 2019), however the social and environmental goals are often subordinated. In addition, some of the reviewed CE policies mainly focus on the waste aspect.

A new Circular Economy Action Plan (2020) provides the most recent CE policy document in Europe. The subtitle: *For a cleaner and more competitive Europe* and its positioning as an important building block of The Green Deal (2019), clarifies the focus of CE: A fully circular economy is essential to become climate neutral in 2050, while strengthening the socio-economic position of Europe. Although this new CE strategy is operative in Europe, the EU member states have yet to follow. This is an essential step towards a common strategy, in which CE is not an end in itself but a means to harmonise and achieve different higher-level goals (Weber & Stuchtey, 2019), such as environmental and social gains.

6.2.1 Circularity indicators

While Circular Economy as a concept already have generated wide recognition as a concept and as a logically and meaningful way forward, it remains less clear how to define adequate indicators in order to measure progress.

As a starting point it could be interesting to understand the current status of circularity in our society. However, this in itself is a difficult question to answer, since there is no harmonised way of measuring circularity.

There are a wide set of indicators available developed by the EEA, JRC and others, however there is a lack of indicators that in a coherent way integrates macro-meso and micro level and cross sectorial synergy.

The work of OVAM⁶ in a project SUMMA⁷, provides a good overview of the different strands of circular economy and associated indicators. The study focuses on a set of 17 indicators and are analysing these for their replicability for Flanders. The following figure provides an overview of the CE indicators classified according to 3 axes: 1) micro/meco/micro level; 2) technology versus socioeconomic and 3) type of CE strategy

In addition, the SUMMA study identifies a number of Circular Economy (CE) indicators more difficult to measure and quantify related mainly to socio-economic aspect such as governance and infrastructure. Of relevance for the URBCON projects, these might include:

- *The degree to which collection, repair, reuse and recycling infrastructure is in place.*
- *Degree to which economic incentives, legislation or comparable rules are in place and enforced regarding product standards, standards for reused or recycled products/raw materials, waste management, better materials management*
- *Degree to which business is involved in managing material cycles in a circular way and is empowered to make the right decisions, either on an obligatory or voluntary basis*
- *Degree to which circular business models are adopted*
- *Degree to which citizens are involved in managing material cycles in a circular way and are empowered to make the right decisions*
- *Degree to which systems are in place for making more efficient use of resources, such as arrangements for sharing products or repairing and reusing them, exchange of information on availability of reusable or recyclable materials (for instance for enhancing industrial symbiosis)*

⁶ <https://www.ovam.be>

⁷ https://circulareconomy.europa.eu/platform/sites/default/files/summa_-_indicators_for_a_circular_economy.pdf

- Degree of information, education and awareness about circular economy (integration into school and university curricula, public communication and information campaigns)
- Degree to which there are voluntary collaboration schemes in place encouraging value chain and cross-sectoral initiatives and information sharing;
- The integration of circular aspects in public procurement schemes
- Product standards related to the defined circular strategies

The following gives an overview of the PROs and CONs of three of the most common CE indicator approaches. As can be seen, whilst the Ellen MacArthurs framework relates to product level, the German Environment Agency focus on the raw material consumption, and finally EUROSTAT for the socioeconomic indicators.

Ellen McArthur Foundation – Material Circularity Indicator (MCI)

Level of Detail:

- micro: product/company
- Fair amount of internal data needed

Pros:

- + Available methodology
- + Simple interpretation

Cons:

- Only material flow
- need of integration with others

MCI = 0.10

German Environment Agency - Raw Material Consumption (RMC)

Level of Detail:

- macro: country/intern. trade
- Available data (Eurostat)

Pros:

- + Available methodology
- + Closely related to DMC

Cons:

- Only material flow accounted
- Expert needed for usage (IOA)

Raw material consumption = Domestic extraction + Imports in RME - Exports in RME

EUROSTAT – Private invest., jobs and GVA: recycling, repair and reuse sect.

Level of Detail:

- meso: region/country

Pros:

- + Job and gross value accounted
- + Close link to CE
- + Available data (Eurostat - NACE)

Cons:

- No clear definition of economic sector (NACE codes uncertainty)

Figure 6-1 Overview of three different CE indicators frameworks

For the purpose of URBCON the RMC approach is likely to provide the most meaningful way of measuring progress towards circularity for the cities involved, however also the socio-economic indicators are important in the regional perspective.

The long-term vision must be to reach 100% circularity of materials and 100% use of sustainable energy supply. Hence, in a perfect circular economy it will look like in the illustration below.

Figure 6-2 Vision for a Perfect Circular Economy

Towards URBCON Circularity indicators

The review provided above gives us a solid base on which to select a coherent set of indicators suitable for the purpose of the URBCON project. The indicators to be used are likely to be a mix of technological indicators and socioeconomic indicators depending also on availability of data. This activity will be further addressed in WP LT 1.2 Circular Economic Model.

7 Policy Gaps and recommendations

Based on the extensive literature review combined with the outcome of the IDEA study, but still not including the lessons learnt from the URBCON pilots regarding both cultural, regulative, procurement, and technical challenges, we have at this stage of the URBCON project identified the following main Policy gaps.

7.1 Policy gaps

7.1.1 Circular Economy Indicators & monitoring

In contrast to climate policies where the baseline, target and indicator are known, the circular economy is missing this explicit information. Following the recent European policy, one of the main goals of CE is contributing to climate neutrality. Therefore, CO₂ emissions is a main indicator for CE as well. Additionally, often used indicators are resource-oriented, such as secondary material usage, recycling rates and waste volumes. Nevertheless, it is generally agreed there is a need for additional suitable indicators to measure the progress of CE (Weber & Stuchtey, 2019).

Over the last years several sets of indicators and methods have been developed, such as the Material Circularity Index (MCI) by Ellen MacArthur foundation and the EU Monitoring Framework. These models either focus on the resource, environmental or economic indicators, yet do not cover it all. Since CE is operating on different stages of the supply chain and levels (micro/meso/macro), it is arguable if a single method is possible. Overall, there is currently no harmonized core method for measuring the progress towards a circular economy available. Although the lack of generally agreed targets and indicators also makes it unclear what exactly should be measured.

A common method for analysing environmental impact is a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA). The results of a LCA study are published in an Environmental Product Declaration (EPD). With the recently approved revision of European standard for EPD's (EN 15804), these methods are improved for reporting circularity: In addition to environmental impact indicators, such as CO₂ emissions, the EPD reports on parameters for input and output of materials, energy and water. Therefore LCA's & EPD's provide a base method for quantifying environmental and resource indicators. However, socio-economic aspects are insufficiently included.

7.1.2 Economic incentives for innovation

One of the major challenges, which has also been addressed by participating market parties in the URBCON project, is the economic feasibility of investing in CE. Since virgin materials are cheaper than secondary materials and recovery of reusable materials is labour intensive and expensive, there is a lack of economic incentive for decision making towards CE (Hartley K, et al. 2020). In order to encourage green innovation and promote market upscaling, financial instruments such as funding for green innovation could be considered. It should be mentioned that the EU's funding programmes, e.g. Horizon2020 and the current Horizon Europe are investing heavily in the green transition and circular economy. Instead, public procurement is to a lesser degree geared towards allowing for innovative solutions. This is a topic currently being explored in the URBCON project as Public procurement is used and challenged during the 3 Pilots, one with the City of Rotterdam and 2 with the City of Ghent. Lessons learnt from these pilots will be reported in later deliverables once the Pilots have finalised.

7.1.3 Taxes

A frequently heard and discussed tax is CO₂, also known as the carbon tax. While several EU member states have introduced carbon taxes, among the UK & France, there is no EU-coordinated taxation

system. As a result, the carbon tax prices among different EU member states currently vary greatly, if implemented at all. Instead, all member states are part of the EU emissions trading system (EU ETS), which introduces a cap and trading system in carbon emission allowance. The EU 'carbon market' is a main policy instrument for introducing a financial incentive to reduce carbon emissions, however, the effectiveness is questioned in comparison to a tax system. Especially the price volatility of the market system, instead of a fixed price with taxes is an often heard criticism. Since more EU member states are introducing CO₂ taxation as additional national regime, the European landscape of carbon taxes is becoming complicated. For uniformity and convenience, the need for a European coordinated tax system is increasing.

Other possibilities to use taxes as a financial instrument is by reducing VAT on secondary product and materials or by reducing corporate taxes, hence making sustainable and circular products cheaper for consumers, thus more attractive. By using taxes in such a way, the concern that extra costs by taxation is being passed onto the consumers is countered. The combination of 'negative' taxes for CO₂ or 'linear' products and 'positive' taxes on VAT for low emission and circular product allows to control the balancing of prices between secondary and virgin materials and products. The Northern Europe countries already make use of a range of financial policies to optimise price differences between unsustainable and sustainable products.

7.1.4 Public procurement

Direct financial incentives through public procurement can be achieved by using sustainable or circular indicators as reward criteria. In this way the tenderers are stimulated in a sustainable or circular manner to achieve a competitive tender. For example in the Netherlands the outcome of LCA studies (*MKI/ECI : Environmental Costs Indicator*) is commonly used as a reward criteria in tenders for construction work. In addition, the tenderer can effectively become more sustainable or circular, since LCA provides insight where environmental impact or use of materials, energy and water occurs throughout the life cycle. In Europe the integration of LCA in public procurement is part of the Strategy for a Sustainable Built Environment. This strategy is due to launch in 2021, therefore the content and its operation is unknown.

According to Witjes & Lozano (2016), the degree of success for a sustainable outcome is depending on the configuration of the public procurement process. When organizing the tendering process with a collaborative approach, the stakes of the process changes from a (price) negotiation between supplier and procurer towards a cooperation to achieve the most value for both parties. For sustainable / circular procurement to succeed, the process needs to shift from an inquiry; based on technical specifications, towards a discussion on technical & non-technical specifications, among socio-economical. This approach has also been found to be essential in the development process of URBCON in order to enable conduction of the pilots with innovative materials. Whilst there is no

standard procedure available, Witjes & Lozona (2016) propose the collaboration framework, shown in Figure 14

Figure 14. Collaboration between procurement and business models for CE (ProBiz4CE) framework. (Witjes & Lozona, 2016)

7.1.5 Information & Data

There is a strong relationship between CE and digitalisation, such as material passports and digital marketplaces, which are also part of the URBCON project. These digital solutions are increasingly becoming necessary to enable development of new business models and processes by means of smart data usage. Since CE is a system approach, the data collection and usage is transcending sectoral boundaries and in case of URBCON even national borders. Therefore, digital solutions ought to be used by, and useful for, all stakeholders in the supply chain; ranging from producers and architects to contractors and recycling parties.

For digital solutions to serve such a wide variety of stakeholders, it is essential to agree upon the use of information models and standards. As an example, Figure 2 provides a visualisation of the Basis Model Geo-information in the Netherlands, provided by the national Standard NEN3610:2011.

Figure 2. Visualisation of the Basic Model Geo-information in The Netherlands (NEN3610:2011)

The NEN3610: 2011 Basic Model Geo-information simplifies the exchange of geo-information between parties and information systems and makes the use of this geo-information unambiguous and meaningful. NEN3610 forms the common basis of the various underlying sectoral information models. It contains the terms, definitions, relationships and general rules for the exchange of information about spatial objects. By use of this model, it allows for different stakeholders to ‘speak’ the same digital language, allowing to interact with each other by exchanging understandable information.

During the development of URBCON Materials passport and digital market place in URBCON, there was no Basic Model for Geo-information found on European level. While the NEN3610 refers to the

INSPIRE European Standards, there is still a need for additional international agreements to have an interchangeable information model among European countries.

7.1.6 Social/Cultural/ Behavioral

The construction and building industry is indeed rather conservative, hence there is an in-built inertia towards change. Ordinary Portland cement is a cheap, well-tested, well-know, universal and global material that only due to its high CO₂ footprint has reached high on the political agenda and are increasingly experiencing a kind of a 'cement-shaming'. Although, the cement industry knows it has to change, it takes a long time to change the culture and perception around it.

The figure below from the work of Thomas Weber et al. summarises very well the main obstacles towards circular economy, and hence where there is room for policy interventions.

* explained by way of example in the text

Figure 7-1. Obstacles to the transformation to a CE (Source: Thomas Weber & Martin Stuchtey, 2019)

7.2 URBCON Policy recommendations

Although there are many positive trends to be observed in the building and construction industry, notably:

- Many policies already being implemented at all level of society, micro, meso and macro

A number of barriers remains that is likely to need policy interventions to be overcome.

At the current stage of the URBCON project, we can put forward the following set of Policy Recommendations:

Barrier	Overall goal	Likely measures
Low prices on virgin materials Low demand on new SRMs	Encourage the use of Secondary raw materials	Taxes on virgin materials Public green procurement
Market inertia and lack of knowledge of carbon footprint on existing procedures	Promote use of low carbon building materials and concepts	Material passport LCA and carbon footprint
Current EN206 cement standard	To allow new types of low carbon cements to be tested and assessed on same terms as current OPC	Shift to Performance-based building standards
Lack of knowledge and awareness of new types of low carbon cement	To encourage stakeholders: architects, civil engineering, construction companies, certification schemes, etc to consider low carbon cements	Demonstration projects Communications Green- public procurement

Public procurement is a key instrument for governments and for achieving the long-term implementation targets of URBCON, hence the deployment of the Strategy for a Sustainable Built Environment should be monitored in the URBCON project.

Common understanding of Circular Economy is essential to determine the goal and set targets. This is a requirement to monitor progress on the circular economy and to adjust the strategy to achieve the objectives, especially for the socio-economic aspect.

In today's economy the use of secondary materials is often financially unattractive. Without interventions through financial policy instruments, scaling up to a fully circular economy is hampered. Additional financial incentives should be applied. Although budgets contribute to stimulating the transition, they do not cover the transformation of the economic system alone. A combination of positive

and negative incentives should compensate for the price difference, such as taxes and by means of reward criteria in tenders.

8 Conclusions

Although there are many positive trends to be observed in the building and construction industry, notable:

- Many policies already being implemented at all level of society, micro-meso and macro
- High interest from private actors to invest in the green transition
- High interest among most stakeholders within the construction industry to move towards circularity
- Market increasingly demanding carbon neutral building materials

A number of barriers remains that is likely to need policy interventions to be overcome.

At the current stage of the URBCON project, policy recommendations focus on the following 3 main subjects:

- Encourage the use of Secondary raw material by introducing measures such as taxes on virgin materials and through specifications in Public Green Procurement
- Allow new types of low carbon cements to be tested and assessed on same terms as current OPC by shifting towards Performance-based building standards
- To encourage stakeholders: architects, civil engineering, construction companies, certification schemes, etc to consider low carbon cements through more demonstrations/reference projects, training and communication and Green Public Procurement

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